

Specific Ways to Sort out Volleyball Players and Prepare Qualified Athletes

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Abstract:

The article discusses the work aimed at the development of volleyball sport, methods of selecting volleyball players in groups using regulatory tests and exercises, the acquisition of skills and abilities in the main forms of techniques and tactics of playing volleyball, as well as ways of their preparation.

Keywords: Selection, club, volleyball, sports and selection, selection, regulatory control, wellness and pre-training groups.

INTRODUCTION.

The tasks of the development of volleyball in sports schools, general education schools, technical and higher educational institutions and its importance are considered one of the most popular sports of volleyball in all educational institutions of the Republic. Volleyball, as an educational activity, is included in the curriculum of all educational institutions. The reason for the strength of so much attention to volleyball is its simplicity and the fact that it is an inexpensive, affordable tool in the physical education system.

"Sports competition" is a multi-year pedagogical process that makes it possible to find promising children who can achieve high results in exactly the same processes that are associated with regular training sessions in a particular sport, including competitions. It is customary to use a set of various regulatory tests (exercises) to organize the competition according to the purpose, objectively assess the educational abilities, mental qualities and functional capabilities acquired in children throughout their offspring and life, accurately predict the signs of talent and future skills in volleyball. Sports competition is inextricably linked with many years of sports training, which is also carried out from the initial stage of mastering sports qualifications at the highest stage, that is, in the activities of national teams.

The concept of "choice" includes the question of "merit", i.e., whether a person is fit or mischievous in one field (specific activity) by talent. This word means that a person has not only his own capabilities (age, physical qualities, mental properties, etc.) to a specific activity (profession, job, sport, etc.) must be appropriate, but it is precisely this activity that is desirable to be worthy of the client of this person (questions of emotion, activation, motivation). The term "choice" again introduces into its composition the concept of "chamalov", which refers to sports. Chambering can be done in kindergartens, schools and elementary groups of sports schools. Proper chambering depends on the talent of the coach, his knowledge and experience. Depending on the offspring of the child, lifestyle indicators, chambering is also of considerable importance.

MAIN PART.

It is necessary that the national teams of our republic not only train highly qualified volleyball players, but also lead the events of growing talented volleyball players, provide them with theoretical and methodological support. Sports competition is a multi-year pedagogical process. Preparing children for the preliminary competition is carried out by a physical education teacher in a school setting, students can be sorted on a program basis and using evaluative exercises, action folk games. It is advisable that these sorting tools are extremely close to the very essence of the game of volleyball. During the preparation process for the preliminary competition, students are required to undergo a regular medical examination. The more qualitative and effective this event is carried out, the higher the level of quality of the competition organized in sports schools. Preliminary selection. Preliminary selection is usually carried out in 3 stages.

Phase I. Propaganda-organize propaganda work, interest, attract students (talk, conduct lectures, show films about volleyball competitions). To organize show competitions, conduct conversations with the participation of famous athletes.

Phase II. Preliminary selection – reception using evaluative exercises, action and folk games (indicators of fate, determination of the development of physical qualities using apparatus, etc.).

Phase III. Initial training I assessment of the special qualities, technical and tactical skills, abilities and capabilities of children during the annual training period. The study of their genealogical qualities.

Conducting a competition for technical and tactical training.

When conducting competitions for sports clubs and sports schools, children can face serious biopedagogical errors in determining the norm of loads applied, increasing their size in a "wave-like" principle in accordance with the dynamics of physical and functional capabilities, if the age, number of people involved and other indicators are not approached in a standard and one order. The special tests "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" introduced in our country are also based on this differentiated system. When conducting competitions, admission and formation of preparatory groups for sports clubs, sports schools, a small (engaged) child with a biologically progressive formation can be transferred to a large age group.

Selection methods, regulatory tests and tools for volleyball.

Pedagogical methods (tests)

1. Body length and weight
2. 30m. run
3. 5x6m. run
4. Vertical jump from place
5. Jump from place to length

6. Throwing the filling Ball (1 kg) from behind the head two supports

Physiological styles:

1. Measurement of the frequency of heart contraction: in a calm state, after a 5-minute jump load and after 5 minutes have passed.
2. Measurement of breathing frequency: in a calm state, after a 5-minute jump load and after 5 minutes.

Psychological styles:

1. Closing the eye stop the stopwatch arrow at "0"
2. 50% differentiation from maximum strength in the hand dynamometer.

The first acquaintance with the game is made through games of the preparatory and close to volleyball movements. For example, a ball pass, which is the main method of play, is strengthened using the following exercises: "transmit-sit", "the ball is in the middle", "the ball is in the air", etc.

Training in technique and solo tactical movements begins with moving around the position and pitch. Improvement is carried out by complicating actions.

Entering the ball into the game begins by teaching the ball to enter straight and sideways from below. Special exercises are taught in the following order:

1. Transfer the ball to the wall from a distance of 6-8 m.
2. Transfer the ball to the partner in the row (without a net).
3. Entering the ball into the game over the net from a short distance.
4. Inclusion in the game from its own line in a certain direction.
5. The same only from the place of inclusion in the game, for a certain period.
6. To enter the ball into the game in turn to different regions.
7. Quick introduction into the game, taking into account accuracy.

Improving the tactics of introducing the ball into the game is carried out with constant control over their effectiveness and regularity in training games and competitions.

Mistakes in getting the ball into the game.

1. Start imperfect and throw the ball up unevenly.
2. Not shaking the hand sufficiently and giving the blow with a bent hand.
3. Wrong hitting the ball with the palm.

Training to pass the ball is carried out with the help of a preparatory, special exercises in the middle position. The fact that the learner clearly visualizes the input technique into the game from above.

More complex ball passes are then taught, ball passes by jumping and acting as if striking, ball passes by falling and rolling over the shoulder. Exercises that strengthen the technical and tactical skills of the ball transfer include solo, pair and group exercises:

1. Ball transfer to the wall in a variety of ways, with varying range, altitude and speed.
2. The same exercise, with a change of posture in front, sitting sideways, lying down, turning 180° and ball passes.
3. The same exercise, but walking right along the wall, to the left, passing a ball from the top and receiving from the bottom.

4. Transfer the ball to different heights with the head in different ways, standing in place and moving along the limiting line.
5. The same exercise, but standing in front of the ball, moving to the right, left, forward, backward
6. To different areas of the attack, uzi threw a second touchdown pass after hitting the ball to the floor with a walk to the net behind the offensive line and a jump to the bouncing ball.
7. The same exercise but with the ball going forward in different zones of the defender and the ball wrapped up in two supports from the bottom.

It is of great importance to perform exercises with a teammate, creating certain conditions for training in ball passing and improving this method.

1. In pairs, ball passes are made in different ways by varying the distance height and the speed at which the ball flies;
2. The same exercise but by changing the moved positions, sitting on a slope from the front, lying down, jumping and turning to 180° and throwing a ball over his head and receiving it from below;

The training and improvement of the ball to receive and pass from the bottom is carried out in the same order as in the ball pass from the top. With this method, the balls introduced into the game are taken by the attacker to take the shots, while performing the application, kicking the balls that are going out to the edge of the field over the ball. In the beginning, the method of receiving the ball from the bottom with two supports is more reliable, since young volleyball players will not be mobile enough yet.

Physical and technical (volleyball) exercises given during training and in academic classes should be normalized, taking into account the functional and physical capabilities of children of different ages and sexes in terms of their size, intensity, complexity and number of returns. The correct distribution of physical and technical-tactical exercises used in the training process determines the effect of training qualified volleyball players. In the process of initial training, the vast majority of exercises should be aimed at the formation of physical and functional training of children, while the rest should be designed to master their technical and tactical skills is one of the important conditions. At this stage, the application of specialized action games to various action games, including a volleyball game, helps to effectively organize the preparation process. It is desirable that such action games be used at all stages of the training and improvement process. At the stage of improvement, gradually the percentage of total exercise is reduced, while the percentage of special physical exercises and technical and tactical exercises increases significantly. The volume of exercises is slightly reduced, the severity and the number of repetitions are increased. In the stage of skill perfection (strengthening), the intensity of exercise execution should be brought to the level of competition. Of great importance at this stage is the fact that most competition exercises are applied in accordance with different game situations. Teaching each play skill (ball input, transmission, stumbling, receiving, kicking) to perform in different ways, such as being able to perform relatively uniformly in the right and left hand of the shot, expands the playing skill's playing range and enriches the movement Reserve. In the process of training and improvement, in order to ensure the effective execution of Game Skills for a long time, physically, technically-tactically, quickly, strongly, dexterously, accurately and in accordance with the situation, in most cases, exercises are performed in the presence of fatigue complications. But, such training is extremely careful to apply darcor. Because, overloading (nagruzka) can expose the child's body to tension, injury or pathological conditions. In the training of young volleyball players, it is important to go to form them in a parallel way, as well as their psychological qualities. As you know, success in a volleyball game or in certain situations of the game requires the formation of qualities of quick thinking, analysis, differentiation, correct assessment, attention, memory, anticipation (perception), willpower, ingenuity, as well as “cunning”, in addition to the high development of all qualities,

skills and abilities. The effectiveness of training talented young volleyball players will largely depend on the purposeful Organization of the selection process in admission to sports clubs and sports schools.

In wellness and preliminary preparation groups, general physical fitness occupies the maximum number of Hours, special physical fitness – less, maintenance – less again, and tactical training occupies the minimum number of hours. In subsequent groups, the volume of training is increasingly directed towards specialization. That is, special physical training will prevail in terms of hours, the volume of technical and tactical exercises will increase.

Conclusion. The tasks of directing children to the sport of volleyball and the methodically correct Organization of qualifying activities, training highly qualified athletes in volleyball are performed. When channeling and sorting children into sports, it is important for them to reach their personal interests and physical abilities. Children can be guided in the sport of volleyball from the age of 11-12 years. The initial training of young volleyball players should be aimed at developing them the qualities of speed, agility, physical qualities that are in accordance with volleyball players. In order for qualifications and skills to be acquired in the basic forms of the technique and tactics of the game of volleyball, training must be carried out. Primarily taught are the volleyball player's jumping, running, sitting, and throwing movements and the techniques of putting a ball into the game, receiving a ball, passing a ball. From tactical actions, skills are formed for participating in the game of volleyball, performing fake actions, fints. Training sessions of young athletes are organized in periods. During the preparatory period, young volleyball players occupy elements of the technique and tactics of the volleyball game, their physical qualities are developed. At the same time, the preparation of spiritual, moral and spiritual Will is organized in young sportists.

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